

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

RESECTION OF TRACHEAL BIFURCATION

Bakhromova Odina

*Master, Tashkent Medical Academy, Faculty of General Surgery
Uzbekistan, Tashkent*

E-mail: azimbaevaodina4@gmail.com

Eshonkhodzhaev O.D - *Associate Professor of Medical Sciences*

Khayaliev R.Ya. - *Candidate of Medical Sciences*

Abstract

Over the past few years, significant advances in surgical and anesthetic techniques as well as appropriate selection of patients have led to an improvement in the immediate and long-term treatment outcomes in patients with non-small cell lung cancer with involvement of tracheal bifurcation. In accordance with the current selection criteria, patients with contralateral lymph node metastases (lung root, aortic window, paratracheal area) require chemotherapy or chemoradiotherapy with subsequent estimation of follow-up and treatment strategy. Surgeries with resection of tracheobronchial bifurcation are considered technically complicated, and they should

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

be performed in carefully selected lung cancer patients and only in specialized centers with extensive experience. It allows the incidence of intra-and postoperative complications to be significantly reduced.

Key words: indications and contraindications, circular resection, surgical treatment, survival rate, pneumonectomy.

RESECTION OF TRACHEAL BIFURCATION

Reconstructive tracheobronchial surgery has more than half a century of history of its development. However, to date, these operations have not become ordinary, standard for many thoracic clinics.

Tracheal bifurcation resection is a technically complex operation, fraught with potential life-threatening complications. Careful patient selection and surgical planning are essential for an optimal outcome.

Resection and plastic surgery of the bronchi and trachea are performed in some of the world's leading clinics, by individual highly qualified surgeons, and the proportion of these operations in the surgical treatment of lung cancer is low. At the same time, despite the development of various diagnostic methods, great success in the early detection of lung cancer has not been achieved, and a large number of patients enter medical institutions with stage III disease.

Many of them have spread of the tumor to a significant part of the main bronchus and the bifurcation of the trachea. For this category of patients, it is impossible to perform radical resection with closing of the bronchus stump using conventional methods -

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

suturing the main bronchus with a mechanical or manual suture. They were shown plastic surgery of the tracheal bifurcation.

Most often, this operation is performed through the right pleural cavity, because. during the operation, with a more extended lesion, it may be necessary to resect the lung of one or another volume, which is preferable to perform through a thoracotomy. The main indication for bifurcation resection is non-small cell lung cancer with carina involvement and no metastases to mediastinal lymph nodes.

Other indications are primary respiratory tract tumors such as glandular cystic cancer and other rare benign and malignant neoplasms.

Other indications are primary respiratory tract tumors such as glandular cystic cancer and other rare benign and malignant neoplasms.

Contraindications for resection of tracheal bifurcation:

- the need for prolonged artificial ventilation of the lungs in the postoperative period
- the use of steroid hormones in history, which are fraught with the occurrence of postoperative complications
- metastases to the mediastinal lymph nodes during surgery for non-small cell lung cancer
- the need for resection of a large section of the trachea, if an anastomosis is planned between the trachea and the left main bronchus
- Radiation treatment of the mediastinal region in history.

Patients with non-small cell lung cancer who are indicated for resection of the tracheal bifurcation require mediastinoscopy to assess the condition of the

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

mediastinal lymph nodes and tracheal bifurcation. Performing remote mediastinoscopy eventually causes fibrosis in the incision plane, complicating subsequent resection.

Resection and plastic surgery of the tracheal bifurcation can be performed in case of central lung cancer or peripheral cancer with centralization (with tumor spread from the lobar bronchus to a significant part of the main bronchus (the proximal edge of the tumor is less than 1.5 cm from the carina) and tracheal bifurcation). Most often, resection of the bifurcation of the trachea is performed with pneumonectomy.

However, if the bronchus of the neighboring lobe or lung lobes is not affected by a tumor, it becomes possible to perform an organ-preserving resection - lobectomy or bilobectomy with resection and plastic surgery of the tracheal bifurcation. This is especially important for patients with low functional reserves who cannot be treated with pneumonectomy.

Depending on the degree of damage to the main bronchus and tracheal bifurcation and the form of tumor growth (exophytic or endophytic), 3 main options for resection of the tracheal bifurcation are performed: circular, wedge-shaped, marginal.

In pneumonectomy with circular resection of the bifurcation of the trachea, the integrity of the airways is restored by anastomosis between the trachea and the main bronchus of the opposite lung end to end with interrupted sutures.

After a wedge-shaped resection, the defect in the wall of the trachea and the opposite main bronchus is sutured in the transverse direction with an interrupted suture, with marginal resection, the sutures are applied in the longitudinal direction. As a suture

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

material at the first stage of the development of reconstructive surgery, lavsan was used on atraumatic needles, then absorbable threads - vicryl, PDS, etc.

In lobectomy and bilobectomy, along with resection of the bifurcation of the trachea, a circular resection of the main bronchus and intact bronchus of the adjacent lobe of the lung is performed. Taking into account the location and type of resection of the tracheal bifurcation, we have developed 15 different options for reconstructive organ-preserving operations. However, the most commonly performed upper lobectomy on the right, lobectomy with marginal resection of the tracheal bifurcation.

Rarely, it is possible and necessary to perform a lobectomy with resection of the tracheal bifurcation on the left. Upper lobectomy on the left with circular resection of the left main bronchus and circular resection of the tracheal bifurcation, which was performed in 1 patient, should be considered unique.

The integrity of the airways was restored by anastomosis between the trachea, the right main and left lower lobe bronchi with the creation of a new tracheal bifurcation. The patient lived for more than 19 years after the operation without a recurrence of the disease.

In all variants of reconstructive operations, regional lymph nodes are removed: ipsilateral bronchopulmonary and paratracheal, pretracheal and bifurcation. It should be noted that during resection of the tracheal bifurcation, good conditions are created for the removal of regional lymph nodes in the same block as the lung. Metastases in regional lymph nodes were detected: N1 - in 27%, N2 - in 68% of patients.

It is a difficult task to ensure adequate ventilation of the lungs during resection and

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

plastic surgery of the tracheal bifurcation. We use ventilation through an oral endotracheal tube, shunt breathing by intubation of the bronchus through the surgical wound, high-frequency injection ventilation of the lungs through a thin catheter. We have developed a scheme for the use of one or another method of lung ventilation, depending on the variant of resection and reconstruction of the tracheal bifurcation and the stage of its implementation.

The use of resection of the tracheal bifurcation in the surgical and combined treatment of non-small cell lung cancer makes it possible to expand the possibilities of radical treatment in patients who are unresectable by the usual method of lung resection. The most difficult should be considered the implementation of lobectomy, bilobectomy with resection of the tracheal bifurcation, as indicated by a higher postoperative mortality. However, the quality of life and long-term results of treatment are much better than with pneumonectomy with resection of the tracheal bifurcation.

Findings

Pneumonectomy with circular resection of the tracheal bifurcation is accompanied by fewer complications, low frequency of non-radical resections, better overall 5-year survival rates with an equal postoperative mortality rate.

LITERATURE

- 1) V.D. Parshin and V.A. Porkhanov. Tracheal surgery with atlas of operative surgery. M 2009
- 2) M. I. PERELMAN TRACHEAL SURGERY
- 3) RESPIRATORY

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

MEDICINE RUSSIAN RESPIRATORY SOCIETY Moscow Publishing House "Littera" 2017 Volume 1 Edited by Academician of the Russian Academy of Sciences A.G. Chuchalin 4) METHODOLOGICAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR STUDENTS FOR A PRACTICAL LESSON ON THE TOPIC: "Surgical Surgery of the Neck" Compilers: Head of the Department, Ph.D., Associate Professor Songolov G.I. Assoc. Department, Ph.D., Galeeva O.P. Methodological recommendations were considered and approved at the meeting of the Department of Operative Surgery and Topographic Anatomy on 23.09.2014 Minutes No. 3 5) "Otorhinolaryngology: A Guide. Volume 2" Vyacheslav Babiyak 6) Starostin Alexander Vadimovich Postoperative complications and their prevention in the surgery of cicatricial stenosis of the trachea 14.01.17 - Surgery 7) Daihes N.A., Vinogradov V.V., Reshulsky S.S., Kravtsov S.A., Osipenko E.V., Isaeva M.L., Krivykh Yu.S., Mikhalevskaya I.A., Borova I.V. MANUAL FOR PATIENTS WHO HAVE UNDERGONE LARYNGECTOMY ... 8) Anyutin R.G. Tracheostomy and tracheotomy in the practice of otorhinolaryngologists. M., 1971. 9) Bystrenin A.V. Surgical tactics in chronic stenosis of the larynx and trachea // Avtoref. Diss. Doct. Honey. Nauk –M., 2003 – 34 p. 10) Zenger V.G., Nasedkin A.N., Parshin V.D. "Surgery of damage to the larynx and trachea". Moscow, "Medkniga", 2007. 11) Kirasirova E.A., Miroshnichenko N.A., Gorban D.G., Lafutkina N.V., Tarasenkova N.N., Piminidi O.K. "The role of nasocomial infection in patients who have undergone ventilation and tracheostomy". VIII Russian Congress of Otorhinolaryngologists "Science and Practice in Otorhinolaryngology", November 10–11, 2009, pp. 273–274. 12)

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

- Lafutkina N.V. "Algorithm for the management of patients who have undergone tracheostomy in the intensive care unit". Abstract 2008. 13) Parshin V.D. "Tracheostomy". "GEOTAR-Media". Moscow, 2008. 14) Trutnev V.K. "Tracheostomy". Moscow. MEDGIZ, 1954. 15) Shuster M.A., Kalina V.O., Chumakov F.I. "Emergency care in otorhinolarinology". M. Meditsina, 1989, pp. 249–262. 16) Grillo H.C. Postintubation tracheal stenosis. Treatment and results.// J/ Torac. Cardiovasc/ Surg/ 1995. 109, p. 486–92.
- 17) Grillo H.C. Surgery of the Trachea and bronchi. – Lond., 2004.
- 18) Chiu H.H., Chen C.M., Hsieh W.F. Tracheoesophageal fistula// Gastrointest. Endosc. – 2004. – Vol. 60. –p. 603–604.
- 19) Howard D.J. Emergency and elective airway procedure: Tracheostomy, cricoidotomy and their variants// Operative surgery Head and Neck. Pt 1. – 4 th ed./ Oxford. 1992. p. 27–44.

